

DEVELOPMENTS OF NOVEL COMPOSITE CELLULAR MATERIALS BASED ON THE AUXETIC CONCEPT

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SUMMARY

The present paper is focused on some novel auxetic composite materials based on a novel RTM production process invented and patented by the some of the authors. The novel materials can well withstand loads and, as such, have a structural function. In the paper the comparison with traditional cores and the effect on the mechanical properties of several types of fibers and resins will be presented.

Keywords: auxetic, cellular solids, Resin Transfer Moulding.

INTRODUCTION

The traditional honeycombs and cores acts mostly as spacer while the novel developed material can well withstand loads and, as such, have a structural function. The peculiar properties of the material developed are largely due to their auxetic geometry. The term auxetic [1] refers to a novel class of materials characterized by negative Poisson ratio, this means that these materials expand when stretched rather than contracting as traditional materials.

Scarpa et al [2] have recently reported a combined analytical, numerical and experimental analysis on the compressive strength of hexagonal chiral honeycombs due to elastic buckling of the unit cells under flatwise compressive loading. Hexagonal chiral honeycombs are cellular structures composed of noncentresymmetric unit cells, with an in-plane negative Poisson's ratio with a value of -1. the compressive strength for low-density ratios was showed to be higher compared to analogous density properties in conventional centresymmetric honeycombs.

In the present paper the development of a novel RTM method to produce a chiral auxetic structure is described. The material obtained has been fully characterized in terms of mechanical properties using numerical and experimental techniques, and the effect of different cores made by combinations of fibers and resins will be described.

Manufacturing method

The key technology for the production of the novel core material is based on the use of resin transfer molding technology combined with a novel tooling method. The manufacturing process has been patented by two of the authors [3]. The resin used for the preparation of the specimens was a vinyl ester resin Distitron VE 370 SC purchased by Polyint (Italy). The glass fibers were S type KCR2(M) (tex 2400g/1000m) purchased by Camelyaf. Two types of hemp fibers were used. The long filaments were purchased from Aurora Silk while the twisted yarn were purchased by .

The specimens were obtained through a RTM technique using a Hypajet MKII as injection machine. The cycle for all specimens was the following: injection at 70°C at a maximum pressure of 1.5bar; curing at 100°C for 3 hr. The mould was kept in an industrial oven purchased by Idrocalor for all the processing cycle.

The specimens were subjected to different mechanical tests according to the ASTM standards. A sample having dimensions 130 X 80 X 25 mm was compressed under displacement control in accordance to the ASTM C 365-00. The out-of-plane shear behaviour of the core was observed during quasi-static and fatigue loading on specimens having dimensions 205 X 174 X 27 mm. The tests were conducted following the ASTM C273-00 standard.

Results

Figure 1 shows some specimens obtained with the proprietary manufacturing method with glass fibers as reinforcement and polyester resin as matrix.

Figure 1 Examples of cellular solids with chiral geometry obtained by RTM.

Under flatwise compressive loading, the mechanical behaviour was initially elastic (stiffness of 150 kN/mm), followed by a significant strain-hardening occurring at a deformation eight times greater than the elastic one, and resulting finally to sudden failure. The measured compressive modulus was 360 MPa, while the compressive strength resulted in 24 MPa.

Intermediate Finite element results show that the shear strain distribution within a rib is not changing significantly in its central area, while the large strain difference between ribs of different orientation to the loading direction was expected considering the relative size of a rib to the specimen. The overall maximum core shear stress was 3.2 MPa, while the core shear modulus was 9.2 MPa. A second specimen (dimensions 200 X 146 X 27 mm) was subjected to shear fatigue loading starting from 50% of the peak strength and increasing up to 75%. The loading – unloading paths remained straight,

although there was evidence that plastic shear deformation was accumulated as the loading level and number of cycles was increasing. At the end of the fatigue test the specimen was reloaded under displacement control up to peak, with subsequent gradual reduction of the loading. The core behaviour remained almost elastic after high load fatigue and monotonous loading up to peak

The hexachiral RTM core has been developed in the context of an initial implementation for shipbuilding constructions. The properties of the materials developed have been therefore compared to commercial cores commonly used in marine applications [4]. The results of the qualitative comparison are summarized in table 1.

Table 1 Comparison between the novel chiral materials and commercial cores

Property	CHIRAL	DIAB Dynicell	DIAB ProBalsa
Drapability	+++	--	---
Compressive Strength	++++	-	-
Shear Strength	++++	-	-
Compressive Modulus	+	+++	-
Shear Modulus	-	-	++

The auxetic cores were compared in terms of mechanical properties with the aforementioned products from DIAB [4]. In order to compare properly the mechanical properties the experimental data were normalized in terms of the weight per unit area .

The volumetric density of the auxetic material was calculated accordingly to the equations proposed by Scarpa et al [2] and Ashby [5] for the cellular materials

The comparison in terms of specific compression strength (Fig.2a) and modulus (Fig.2b) are reported in Fig.2.

Fig.2a Non dimensional compressive strength

Fig.2b Non dimensional compressive modulus

The data clearly show that the auxetic material outperform the PVC cores of the series Dynicell. The auxetic material has an enhanced behavior compared to balsa in terms of strength, while it has a slightly lower modulus. The better performance is largely due to the peculiar cell geometry of the auxetic systems selected for this study. The cell (fig.3) is characterized by the presence of a central cylinder (which is stabilized laterally by six ligaments). Cylinders are well known to behave better in compression compared to other geometries. The ligaments contribute further to increase the compression strength.

Fig.3 Cell geometry

The unit cell geometry of the hexachiral honeycomb can be defined in terms on the nondimensional parameters α (L/r), β (t/r) and gauge thickness (d/l), where d is the height of the unit cell. Flatwise compressive nonlinear finite element models based on solid elements and elasto-plastic material properties (the composite core) have been developed and benchmarked against flatwise and shear loading experimental tests [6, 7]. The validated models have been used to perform parametric analysis on the specific shear and compressive strength of the hexachiral configurations, varying the cell wall aspect ratio (α) and gauge thickness. Figure 4 shows a carpet plot for the specific compressive strength of the hexachiral honeycomb. The higher values correspond to small gauge thickness and low cell wall aspect ratio, with a variation of α^{-1} and $(d/l)^{-2}$ for increasing nondimensional cell parameters values. The specific compressive strength behaviour is compatible with the one observed for the out-of-plane elastic mechanical properties [6, 7].

For the industrial hexachiral honeycomb developed ($\alpha = 4.4$, $\beta = 0.22$, $d/l = 2$) Fig.5 shows a comparison related to the specific shear strength (a) and modulus (b).

Fig.4a Non dimensional shear strenght

Fig.5b Non dimensional shear modulus

The auxetic materials perform better than traditional materials in terms of shear strength but present lower shear modulus values. The latter results is due to the geometry of the system that, for shear loading, is not optimized. It is easy to understand that for some ligaments the loads are not directed along the fiber direction. For this reason such ligaments will deform more thus leading to higher deformation of the cell. This behavior leads to lower shear modulus compared to PVC cores. Further improvements in the cell design or some changes in the reinforcing materials will aid to overcome this limitation.

An important advantage of auxetic materials over traditional cores (especially honeycomb ones) is the deformation under bending. Honeycomb materials deform in a saddle shape when bent, thus limiting the possibility to conform to single or complex curved shapes. To overcome this limitation, it is common industrial practice to produce honeycomb cores with larger thickness, and then machined to the thickness and shape needed. Cellular solids, like Dynicell, are rigid at room temperature and can not be bent. To solve this problem the stitching of a rectangular element has been proposed as a solution. This solution allows to bend the cellular panel but leads to the creation of resin rich pockets that can become the zones where cracks can form.

The auxetic materials realized in the present paper show a synclastic curvature, meaning that they can be bent without saddle effect [8]. Fig.5 shows an example of a chiral panel in RTM (right) with curvature of radius of 3 m and, for comparison the saddle effect of a standard aluminum honeycomb (left). The possibility of producing curved panel is a clear advantage for some structures such as, for example, boat hulls antennas and duct liners.

Fig.6 Saddle effect: aluminum honeycomb (left) vs auxetic core (right)

Conclusions

The industrial technology developed by the University of Catania and presented here leads to several advantages compared to traditional core materials. The field of auxetics is still the subject of an intense research for several groups in Europe and in the World. The technology presented in the paper has won the International Polymer Challenge 2008 competition. Featured applications are being currently developed also for aerospace applications.

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